

Research

Explicative Molecular Dynamics Simulation Emphasizing Energy Transitions and Adsorption Thermodynamics: CH₄ and Anthracite Sorbates

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Abstract: There are many sources of CH₄ gas, both artificial and natural. Coal seams are a primary natural source, and mining activities contribute immensely to greenhouse gas emissions. Adsorption, a fundamental component in the storage and transport of CH₄ in coal seams, provides sufficient insights for research and application involving CH₄ and/or coal while outlining temperature effects that expose differentia. Molecular dynamics simulation, a towering computational technique that has been utilized in many fields of science and engineering in recent decades to study the behavior and properties of materials from a molecular and atomistic perspective, provides an intrinsic insight into materials as they undergo varying conditions, giving understanding of basic and complex phenomena in many scientific disciplines is used to highlight temperature influence at 273.15K, 333.15K and 393.15K during CH₄ adsorption on anthracite surface under isothermal condition. This study details the molecular simulation (Grand Canonical Monte Carlo simulation) methodology and analyzes potential and kinetic energy transitions coupling temperature dynamics and their effect on adsorption. Two forcefields were considered, COMPASS III and universal forcefields, to which COMPASS III edged. The energy transitions between potential and kinetic energy show that kinetic energy initiates the adsorption process, i.e., sorbates in isolation, while potential energy dominates adsorption phenomenon (sorbates in adsorbed state). The interaction of CH₄ and anthracite, underscored by the first law of thermodynamics, determines adsorption with CH₄ releasing energy, dominating the adsorption process and promoting sorbates interaction while van der Waals force, a distance-dependent parameter, dominates the adsorption phenomenon.

Keywords: Physisorption, Thermodynamics, Molecular Dynamics Simulation, Quantum Chemistry, Computational Chemistry

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1. Introduction

CH₄ has been a source of major hazards in many industries and environments, leading to severe injuries and deaths. The occurrence of CH₄ during coal's maturation provides a traceable trajectory to continuously assess varying conditions. The thermal conditions surrounding coal formation remain an influential factor even post-maturation. CH₄, an unconventional natural gas, a primary hydrocarbon with solid atomic bonds, provides a prerequisite for continuous in-depth investigation amidst unpredictable occurrences. Coal seam is a natural habitat for CH₄, also known as coal seam gas (CSG).[1] The CH₄ content of coal seams is an important parameter for the assessment of CH₄ hazards in hazardous coal mines, as well as the control, storage, and recovery of CH₄ gas.[2, 3] The occurrence of CH₄ stored in coal seam ranges from free/bulk phase, absorption phase, and/or adsorption phase. Coal is a complex, porous, structured sedimentary rock with high chemical and physical heterogeneity. However, coal and coal products such as CH₄ gas play an increasingly important role in fulfilling the energy needs of our society.[4] Over the years, significant research has been done utilizing coal for energy generation.[5] Outbursts in the coal mining industry have also been a major hazard that has gained attention in recent years, even with so many research efforts directed toward control and prevention.[6, 7] A dominant state of CH₄ storage in coal seam is sorption also known as adsorption. The sorption behavior of CH₄ has also been a primary focus of recent studies investigating CH₄ behavioral properties. Sorption in porous coal media is reliant on the van der Waals force of attraction between the CH₄ gas molecules and the coal surface.[8] Isothermal conditions affect adsorption capacity, occurrence, and the state of CBM. Highlighting the temperature influence on the adsorption efficiency via Molecular Dynamics Simulations, we purposely emphasized temperature impact and minimized the maximum fugacity pressure at a level where adsorption is plausible yet exerts less impact. Adsorption isotherms of CH₄ on coal have been established by many researchers, highlighting the proportionality between the adsorption amount, pressure, temperature, etcetera. Hao et al.[9] investigated the methane adsorption characteristics on coal surfaces above critical temperatures and proposed that the temperature dependence on the Langmuir parameter, assuming a homogeneous surface, is not strictly true for methane on coal. Wang et al.[10] investigated the temperature influence on methane sorption and kinetics in coal, and his finding depicts that methane adsorption capacity is enhanced at low temperatures (under 273.15K). From a Molecular Dynamics simulation perspective, Zhang et al.[11] indicated that the absolute adsorption divided by bulk density is independent of temperature (308K & 370K) when pressure is over 8MPa. Molecular dynamics simulation possesses inherent tools that provide many intrinsic insights, dealing with complex systems at molecular levels while providing convenience for experiments. Nevertheless, challenging conditions such as forcefield selections, parameter configurations, and simulation period are all despairing conditions that could undermine accuracy and efficiency, hence the need for a more explicit simulation. This study explicitly explains the simulation process that justifies calibrations, especially forcefields and summation methods. CH₄ and anthracite coal (hereinafter referred to as anthracite) adsorption provides a broader study scope, including but not limited to energy, material science, environmental science, etcetera. In addition to the simulation tools, the anthracite structure used in this simulation is from a single coal mine. As such, the results for other anthracite coal structures may slightly differ. CH₄ molecule and anthracite coal were investigated separately under ambient isothermal conditions, specifically highlighting potential, kinetic, non-bond, van der Waals, and the total adsorption energy and their corresponding specific thermal conditions as they undergo simulation. With energy dynamics being at the center, temperature influence was magnified while pressure (a major external adsorption influencer) involvement was sufficiently minimized for emphasis.

2. Molecular Dynamics Simulation

2.1 Forcefield Selection

Forcefield selection is crucial for accuracy and reliability in Molecular Dynamics Simulation. It describes atomistic and molecular interactions, considering angles, lengths of bonds, and nonbonded interactions such as van der Waals and electrostatic interactions, as well as many other relevant features. We considered just two forcefields, COMPASS III and universal forcefields. Materials Studio COMPASS III, an ab initio forcefield, was prioritized for forcite geometric optimization and dynamics and the sorption isotherm, which enables accurate prediction of structural, conformational, vibrational, and thermophysical properties for a broad range of molecules in isolation and condensed phases under a wide range of temperature and pressure conditions.[12, 13] The universal forcefield, which encompasses a broader scope of elements on the periodic table and molecular structures, preferable amidst complexities, was also considered, yet, COMPASS III was preferred for the simulations.[14] [15] Forcite module energy task was used to determine the applicability of the forcefields, and the results are shown in **Table 1 and Table 2.**

Parameter	Methane (KJ/mol)	Anthracite (KJ/mol)
Valence energy (diag. terms)	9.113	10713463.830
Bond	8.130	415130.066
Angle	0.983	9430091.183
Torsion	0.000	868242.584
Inversion	0.000	0.000
Valence energy (cross terms)	1.310	-5.971
Stretch-Stretch	0.205	0.247
Stretch-Bend-Stretch	1.121	0.414
Stretch-Torsion-Stretch	0.000	-0.732
Separated-Stretch-Stretch	0.000	0.000
Torsion-Stretch	0.000	-4.912
Bend-Bend	-0.018	0.004
Torsion-Bend-Bend	0.000	-0.113
Bend-Torsion-Bend	0.000	-0.879
Non-bond energy	0.000	241298.514
van der Waals	0.000	228073.999
Electrostatic	0.000	13367.031
Total energy	10.421	10954756.380

Table 1: Forcite Energy Evaluation Results for COMPASS III Forcefield (CH₄ and Anthracite)

Parameters	Methane (KJ/mol)	Anthracite (KJ/mol)
Valence energy	5.188	15883443
Bond	5.188	261915.400

Angle	0.000	15611456.00
Torsion	0.000	10071.760
Inversion	0.000	0.000
Non-bond energy	0.000	15697558.000
van der Waals	0.000	15697720
Electrostatic	0.000	-162.009
Total Energy	5.188	31581001

Table 2: Forcite Energy Evaluation Results for Universal Forcefield (CH₄ and Anthracite)

The universal forcefield accounts for fewer energy parameters than the COMPASS III forcefield. As an ab initio forcefield, COMPASS III captures a wide range of parameters, unlike the universal forcefield, which covers many elements but fewer parameters.[16, 17] While focusing on specific parameters contributing to the simulation’s intent, it is important to stay updated on the status of other surrounding parameters, hence the selection of the COMPASS III forcefield.

2.2 Modeling and Optimization

CH₄ and anthracite molecular structures were modeled using Materials Studio Visualizer.[18, 19] Fig. 1 depicts the amorphous structures. The efficiency and accuracy of the simulations were enhanced using materials studio forcite module geometric optimization task for energy minimization to obtain a proper and efficient molecular structure for CH₄ and anthracite models, respectively.[20] The optimized structures are shown in Fig. 2 **Error! Reference source not found.** and their respective detailed energy configurations from the optimization tasks are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. Anthracite optimization preferred the universal forcefield due to molecular complexity (high elements multiplicity).

Fig. 1: Optimized (a) Anthracite (b) CH₄ Structures

Parameter	Energy(kJ/mol)
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Valence energy (diag. terms)	4.254
Bond	0.140
Angle	4.114
Torsion	0.000
Inversion	0.000
Valence energy (cross terms)	-0.35
Stretch-Stretch	0.000
Stretch-Bend-Stretch	-0.298
Stretch-Torsion-Stretch	0.000
Separated-Stretch-Stretch	0.000
Torsion-Stretch	0.000
Bend-Bend	-0.070
Torsion-Bend-Bend	0.000
Bend-Torsion-Bend	0.000
Non-bond energy	0.000
Van der Waals	0.000
Electrostatic	0.000
Total energy	3.906

Table 3: Detailed Results from CH₄ Energy Optimization

Parameter	Energy(kJ/mol)
Valence energy (diag. terms)	8840.982
Bond	2317.600
Angle	3637.507
Torsion	2836.474
Inversion	49.419
Non-bond energy	9671.443
van der Waals	9671.443
Electrostatic	8840.982
Total energy	18512.425

Table 4: Detailed Results from Anthracite Energy Optimization

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Energy Transitions (Kinetic and Potential Energy)

Forcite Dynamics Simulation allows investigating atoms' movements in an atomic structure under computed forces. The temperature and energy configurations were examined under specific parameters in separate CH₄ molecule and anthracite simulations. The COMPASS III forcefield was selected, and the nose thermostat was used to calibrate the ambient temperature for the simulation. In contrast, the thermal energy and temperature of the molecular structures were calculated as they exchanged heat with their environment (thermodynamic condition).[21, 22]

3.1.1 Dynamics Simulation at 273.15K

The overall energy level of the structures in isolation was calculated and the results are shown in Table 5. The results indicate a massive temperature drop across the initial to final stages of the simulation, leading to an infeasible decrease in the kinetic energy and an increase in potential energy for both CH₄ and anthracite. A subsequent increase in total energy was observed, a rare occurrence demanding keen observation and consideration for analysis. CH₄ experiences a higher temperature drop than anthracite, with the average temperature of anthracite being higher, not so wide a margin compared to the temperature drop. The graphical representations for energy and temperature configurations at ambient temperature 273.15K are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. **Error! Reference source not found.**, respectively.

Parameter	CH ₄			Anthracite		
	Initial	Final	Average	Initial	Final	Average
Total energy (kJ/mol)	11.155	11.832	11.535	5939.418	5976.689	5961.334
Potential Energy (kJ/mol)	0.933	10.075	6.510	4423.463	5230.255	5114.601
Kinetic Energy (kJ/mol)	10.222	1.761	5.025	1515.955	746.434	846.729
Temperature (K)	273.150	47.045	134.249	273.150	134.495	152.567

Table 5: Forcite Dynamics Energy and Temperature Configurations at 273.15K

CH₄ temperature curve in Fig. 3 corresponds with the kinetic energy curve in Fig. 2. **Error! Reference source not found.**[23] Temperature change frequency of CH₄ molecule over time is very high compared to anthracite, as expected. Although anthracite attained a higher average temperature as shown in Table 5, CH₄ temperature reached a higher temperature during the simulation. CH₄ average potential energy slightly edges average kinetic energy, while anthracite's average potential energy exceeds kinetic energy by a king-sized margin. This shows an obvious high dynamism for CH₄ molecule and the exact opposite for anthracite. CH₄ and anthracite energy curves for potential and kinetic energies in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show energy conservation within the system. The CH₄ total energy is highly unstable, and anthracite displays almost the exact opposite. Non-Bond Energy being higher than kinetic energy indicates fewer movements or vibrations for anthracite, which is essential for adsorption. Non-bond energy is a major contributor to surface-free energy during adsorption. The result shows a favorable condition for adsorption.

Fig. 2: Forcite Dynamics Energy Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 273.15K

Fig. 3: Forcite Dynamics Temperature Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 273.15K

3.1.2 Dynamics Simulation at 333.15K

Compared to results in Table 5, the energy and temperature levels in Table 6 are higher, resulting from increased ambient temperature for both CH₄ and anthracite. However, the patterns in Table 5 and Table 6 are identical, with a temperature drop over time leading to increased potential energy and reduced kinetic energy for both CH₄ and anthracite. A reduction in the gap between the average potential energy and kinetic energy for CH₄ was observed while anthracite maintained a colossal margin.

Parameter	CH ₄			Anthracite		
	Initial	Final	Average	Initial	Final	Average
Total Energy (kJ/mol)	13.113	13.82	13.502	6272.410	6318.807	6300.150
Potential Energy (kJ/mol)	0.649	10.74	6.853	4423.463	5401.640	5258.815
Kinetic Energy (kJ/mol)	12.464	3.075	6.653	1848.951	917.166	1041.335
Temperature (K)	333.15	82.233	177.75	333.15	165.258	187.631

Table 6: Forcite Dynamics Energy and Temperature Configurations at 333.15K

The curves in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 are also synonymous to Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 indicating the minimum impact of temperature change/increase. A dim difference is yet observable with CH₄ temperature and energy graphs displaying a different pattern. The anthracite temperature curve in Fig. 5 shows a difference for a brief stint under 0.01ps and the energy curves for potential and kinetic energy in Fig. 4 depicts a slightly more sinusoidal curve than Fig. 2. The CH₄ temperature maintains high frequency and corresponding similar energy changes, indicating menial change due to temperature change/increase.

Fig. 4: Forcite Dynamics Energy Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 333.15K

Fig. 5: Forcite Dynamics Temperature Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 333.15K

3.1.3 Dynamics Simulation at 393.15K

The maximum simulation temperature, i.e., 393.15K, represents a different order of magnitude and graphical representations for the CH₄ energies in Fig. 6, and the temperature changes over time, as shown in Fig. 7. The order of magnitude for CH₄ and anthracite average energy in Table 7 corresponds with CH₄ and anthracite average energy in Table 5 and Table 6. The pint-sized energy difference between potential and kinetic energies for CH₄ also shows obvious dynamism and a more relaxed structure, as shown by the difference between potential and kinetic energies for

anthracite. Amidst similitude in configurations, the overall energy levels continue to increase, and graphical representations reflect those fine changes.

Parameter	CH ₄			Anthracite		
	Initial	Final	Average	Initial	Final	Average
Total energy (kJ/mol)	15.359	15.874	15.627	6628.840	6653.997	6646.112
Potential Energy (kJ/mol)	0.649	13.360	8.180	4423.463	5628.599	5494.281
Kinetic Energy (kJ/mol)	14.711	2.515	7.448	2205.377	1025.398	1151.831
Temperature (K)	393.150	67.233	199.066	393.150	197.819	220.008

Table 7: Forcite Dynamics Energy and Temperature Configurations at 393.15K

However, at 393.15K, obvious changes show a significant impact of temperature change/increase, including frequency, sinusoidal pattern, smoothness, etcetera. CH₄ potential and kinetic energy curves experienced a massive frequency reduction coupled with a change in the smoothness, becoming less smooth, as shown in Fig. 6, accounting for an even higher dynamism. The CH₄ energy curve corresponds with the temperature curve in Fig. 7 with temperature and kinetic energy maintaining coherence. There are not so many visible changes for anthracite in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7; only the previous sinusoidal observation in Fig. 4 becomes more visible in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Forcite Dynamics Energy Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 393.15K

Fig. 7: Forcite Dynamics temperature Configurations (CH₄ and Anthracite) at 393.15K

3.2 Adsorption Energy Configurations and Temperature Influence

Physical adsorption includes van der Waals interactions and Electrostatic attraction between molecules. However, adsorption depends on molecular van der Waals forces of mutual attraction between gaseous and solid molecules.[24] Thermodynamic interactions between the CH₄ molecules and the anthracite surface illustrated by the sorption isotherm energies provide clinical insights into the sorption behavior while predicting the equilibrium state. The interaction energy between the CH₄ molecules and the anthracite surface is peculiar to the shape and properties of the sorption isotherm. The energy distribution of the CH₄ molecules along the anthracite surface seeks a specific energy state as the molecules seek to attain an equilibrium state. The temperature influence on adsorption energy is a complex conundrum in that different conditions are applied to the CH₄ molecules, coal, and both CH₄ and coal in adsorbed state. An increase in temperature of the system increases the average kinetic energy of the CH₄ molecules, making adsorption difficult to attain, while the surface energy decreases with an increasing temperature, thus enhancing the possibility as the carbon atoms on the surface of the anthracite try to attract the surrounding CH₄ molecules to reduce their specific surface energy reaching adsorption equilibrium.[25] CH₄ dynamism and specific surface energy are required to attain an equilibrium state during adsorption. Research efforts have been made to determine surface energy for anthracite coals. Kang et al. assessed the surface energy of anthracite coal and the temperature dependence based on mechanical testing and proposed that the surface energy of specimens decreased with increasing pressure.[25] Gang et al. investigated the influence of temperature on coal's adsorbing capability and concluded that gas adsorption decreases with an increase in temperature.[26] Zhang et al. conducted a review and statistical analysis on the influence of temperature on CH₄ adsorption, analyzing the temperature-dependent adsorption of CH₄ on coal, cataloging experimental conclusions from 28 researchers publications from 1995 to 2017 with nineteen (19) experiments involving anthracite coals and the results show CH₄ adsorption capacity of coal decreases as temperature increases.[27-29] Zhang and many others' general consensus does not expel continuous investigations into temperature's behavior and/or influence on the absorption process, with many insights still left to be unraveled. The results from the molecular simulation establish energy contributions during adsorption, keen on van der Waals energy and CH₄ energy distribution along anthracite surface. COMPASS III forcefield was assigned to investigate intrinsic atomistic interactions between CH₄ molecules and anthracite surface. The summation method for the electrostatic terms was grouped while van der Waals was atomized due to the focus on surface interactions as shown in **Table 8**. Evident by Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13 the electrostatic energy contributions are exceedingly minimal, with the same condition applied to the intramolecular forces for the exact same purpose.

Parameters	Electrostatic terms	Van der Waals terms
Summation method	Group based	Atom-based
Cutoff distance	15.5 Å	15.5 Å
Buffer width	0.5 Å	0.5 Å

Table 8: Calculations Parameters (Molecular Dynamics Simulation)

For a more accurate representation of the adsorption thermodynamics, fugacity pressure ranged between 0.01MPa to 0.1MPa which affected adsorption overall capacity yet highlighted temperature influence on adsorption.[30] At low pressures, fugacity can be approximately equivalent to pressure.[31]

3.2.1 CH₄ Energy Distribution and Anthracite Energy Dynamics

A balance of attractive forces, surface interactions, and energy changes characterizes the thermodynamic behavior of CH₄ and coal during the adsorption process. The energy distribution state of CH₄ contact with the anthracite surface is shown in Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10 also depicts the exothermicity of the adsorption process.[32] The similarities in the figures emphasize the menial temperature effect with Table 9 highlighting their numerical distinctions. The smoothness

of the distribution curve depicts the normalization of the probability density function in the application's current equilibrium state. A normal distribution of the CH₄ molecules entails an equilibrium state. It is evident from our results that increasing temperature will reduce equilibrium. At 273.15K, the lowest temperature of the set, there is a higher P(E), i.e., the probability of attaining a suitable energy state from a CH₄ perspective is high, as shown in Fig. 8. As temperature increases, the probability of reaching adsorption equilibrium continues to decrease along with bimodality as shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. An indication that high temperature CH₄ does not favor adsorption. The entropy of CH₄ gaseous molecules provides mobility as CH₄ seeks low energy sites along anthracite for adsorption. However, at higher temperatures, CH₄ possesses higher kinetic energy, which could undermine adsorption. The need for effective pressure couldn't be more emphasized at a higher temperature; hence, the selection of a low pressure range exposes temperature dependency. CH₄ fugacity is approximately equivalent to the CH₄ pressure, and as such, the behavior of the CH₄ molecules determines the fate of the adsorption has been empowered by temperature via energy transitions, an ideal condition for CH₄ is easily achievable. CH₄ is introduced into the simulation cell with high kinetic energy similar to the transport process in anthracite micropores with increased cover time and changes in changes in caring conditions, including pressure, kinetic energy is reduced as CH₄ comes in contact with anthracite surface distributing energy to attain thermodynamic equilibrium and attain adsorption hence the visual exothermicity of Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10. At thermal equilibrium, the particle distribution of the system is described by the Boltzmann distribution curve. Boltzmann distribution describes the statistical distribution of particles in a system at thermal equilibrium. It gives the probability of a particle in a specific energy state of a system having different energies. At different energy levels, the behavior and characteristics of the system are described, and the likelihood of finding an energy state is predicted in a state of thermal equilibrium.[33] The CH₄ molecules subscribe to the Boltzmann distribution theory, seeking adsorption on the anthracite surface. The energy distribution influences the CH₄ molecules' probability of adhering to specific sites along the anthracite surface.

The probability of finding a particle in a specific energy state is proportional to the negative exponential of the energy divided by the product of Boltzmann's constant and the temperature. The equation is given as:

$$P(E) = Ce^{\frac{-E}{kT}} \quad (1)$$

where P(E) is the probability of the particle being in an energy state; e is the base of the natural logarithm; E is the energy state of the system; k is Boltzmann's constant; T is the temperature of the system

The electrostatic and intramolecular energy results shown in Fig. 11, Fig. 12 **Error! Reference source not found.**, and Fig. 13 **Error! Reference source not found.**, validate the summation assertion shown in Table 8. The adsorption energy (energy released during the adsorption process) is from both CH₄ and anthracite in adsorbed state. Reacting to the CH₄ in contact with anthracite surface, specific surface energy influences the interactions between CH₄ molecules and anthracite surface. During the isothermal adsorption process of CH₄ in coal, the enthalpy of the coal surface is affected by the energy released by the methane gas molecules, causing a thermodynamic change.[34] Energy change enables adsorption and has a huge effect on the adsorption capacity of coal. The surface energy of the coal occurs because of a balanced state or lost interactions due to porosity. The carbon atoms on the surface of the coal attract the surrounding gas molecules to reduce their specific surface energy and thus reach equilibrium.[25] Generically, the specific surface energy is the quotient of the surface energy by the surface area. However, the specific surface energy variation for a single layer at each fugacity point can be given by:[35]

$$\Delta\sigma_{P_1} = \frac{abRT}{V_0S(1 + bP)} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{P_1}$ is the specific surface energy variation at fugacity P_1 ; a is the saturated adsorption capacity; b is the adsorption equilibrium constant; R is the ideal gas constant; T is the temperature; V_0 is the molar volume; S is the specific surface area; P is the relative pressure

However, the adsorption phenomenon is the beginning of anthracite’s exothermicity as shown in Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13. The total and average energy results indicate coinciding with the van der Waals energy is a clear indication of van der Waals energy’s significance to the adsorption phenomenon. Van der Waals energy is an accurate determination of the interaction energy, a preference when analyzing adsorption. Van der Waals energy is a result of van der Waals force, in this case, van der Waals forces of attraction. Van der Waals forces exist among all kinds of atoms and molecules. The origin of van der Waals force stems from the instantaneous dipole-induced dipole interactions among adjacent apolar atoms and molecules, which can be repulsive or attractive. Among polar molecules, there are three components that contribute to the total van der Waals forces: the induction force, the orientation force, and the dispersion force.[36-38]

Parameters	393.15K	333.15K	273.15K
Maximum Energy(kJ/mol)	-187.652	-186.816	-185.560
Minimum Energy(kJ/mol)	-132.424	-134.097	-142.465
Energy range (kJ/mol)	-55.228	-52.719	-43.095
Maximum P(E)	0.289	0.313	0.380
Maximum P(E) Energy(kJ/mol)	-172.59	-171.335	-175.937

Table 9: CH₄ Energy Distribution Summary Results

Fig. 8: CH₄ Energy Distribution at 273.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

Fig. 9: CH₄ Energy Distribution at 333.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

Fig. 10: CH₄ Energy Distribution at 393.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

Fig. 11: Adsorption Phenomenon Energy Configurations at 273.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

Fig. 12: Adsorption Phenomenon Energy Configurations at 333.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

Fig. 13: Adsorption Phenomenon Energy Configurations at 393.15K (Thermodynamic Equilibrium)

At 393.15K, maximum energy is released, which favors the adsorption process (an exothermic process), followed by temperatures 333.15K and 273.15K, with the energy range following a similar pattern. The maximum P(E) pattern is the opposite. The Maximum P(E) energy follows an opposite ordonnance coupling smoother curves in direct proportions. A smooth CH₄ distribution curve for CH₄ adsorption on a coal surface indicates a consistent and uniform interaction between CH₄ molecules and anthracite, a positive indication of the characteristics of CH₄ adsorption on coal surfaces, implying uniformity in the adsorption process. Thermodynamically, this implies uniformity in the adsorption process and potentially reflects thermodynamic stability within the system, indicating effective CH₄ adsorption under the studied conditions. The contributions of temperature towards the thermal energy of the system cannot be unnoticed, which is a key component aiding CH₄ molecules to exceed activation energy.[39] From Table 9 it's obvious that at a higher temperature, the system(adsorption interface) is prone to higher thermal energy; therefore, if a higher energy probability can be obtained via another nondisruptive medium, perhaps pressure, we could obtain more efficient adsorption at a higher temperature but not so high that CH₄ molecules do not adhere to attractive forces due to high kinetic energy.[23]

Conclusion(s)

The energy transitions between potential and kinetic energy while maintaining constant total energy depict energy conservation. CH₄ (adsorbate) and anthracite (adsorbent) in isolation and adsorbed phases provide a bit of a conundrum

for temperature during adsorption due to behavioral variation of sorption components (adsorbate and adsorbent) at different stages of the adsorption process. Van der Waals energy experiences very minimum or no energy change at temperatures 273.15K, 333.15K, and 393.15K, which suggests that the temperatures do not pose sufficient direct threat to the adsorption process and, as such, are suitable for adsorption. The strength of van der Waals forces as a distant dependent parameter is negatively affected by rapid CH₄ mobility. CH₄ energy distribution curves depict a very rough anthracite surface and difficult adsorption as temperature increases. While a certain degree of entropy is encouraged, there are prevailing conditions to which the CH₄ molecules should be subjected, such as van der Waals force of attraction, hence the importance of influential factors like pressure. Finally, forcefield selection and parameter calibration are crucial in molecular dynamics simulation and have an essential influence on the simulation's results. Adsorption thermodynamics of CH₄ and anthracite are determined by the CH₄ energy distribution and the van der Waals (coal surface) reaction all influenced by external factors such as temperature and pressure for efficient adsorption.

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